

**By forming labor education in preschool children
education of moral qualities.**

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Abstract: Ways and means of educating moral qualities in preschool children through the formation of labor education are analyzed. Thoughts and opinions about preparing children for life through work were analyzed.

Key words: Labor education, moral education, aesthetic education, self-service, work in nature, work of adults, household work, manual work.

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The issue of providing labor education to the young generation is the most urgent topic at the present time. Work plays an important role in the development of each person and the development of society as a whole. Labor education is important in the physical, intellectual, moral and aesthetic upbringing of children of preschool age. Work is organized taking into account the specific characteristics of children of each age group, and sufficient results can be achieved only with proper guidance. The specific aspects of children's work of preschool age have been widely studied in scientific works conducted by many scientists. The main goal of labor education is to develop children in all aspects, to bring them up morally, to mentally prepare them for future work activities, to inculcate the desire to work. The tasks of labor education are diverse, so they are divided into categories as follows. The tasks of the first group are determined by pedagogical influence on the independent work of children:

1. To teach children to set goals, to choose the necessary materials and work tools according to labor qualifications, skills, labor culture.

To teach children to appreciate the work of adults and to appreciate the value of work through the formation of future work activities in children, the distribution of work flows among those who participate in work, and the formation of skills to achieve good results in work

3. Forming the initial social reasons for labor activity, achieving labor results by arousing interest in objects and actions, and understanding the social importance of labor in large groups. The tasks of the second group are aimed at fostering a positive attitude towards the work of adults:

1) To explain to children what results adults are working to achieve.

2) Cultivate children's respect for working people, desire to help them as much as possible.

3) Teaching adults to preserve the results of work.

The tasks of the third group are aimed at forming the child's personality in work activities:

- Cultivating in children hard work, participation in any kind of work, sparing no effort to finish the work they started, and the right attitude towards their personal work.

- Cultivating the moral qualities of a child's personality, such as responsibility, independence, goal orientation, determination, initiative and activity, patience, endurance.

- Cultivating cultural behavior and a positive attitude towards one's peers, being able to work together in mutual agreement, participating in team work until the result is achieved, objectively evaluating the work of oneself and one's peers, helping, etc. Thus, labor activity is formed during preschool age. Under the guidance of a teacher, all important aspects of the social causes of work are formed. Knowledge of adult work and its social importance is acquired.

The word ethics is derived from the Latin word "myeros", which means moral, logic, and it is a social law that is not strictly written down anywhere. Man uses moral norms in his daily life.

The norms of moral education are the basis of the legal norms of every society. In moral education, a person who not only acquires moral knowledge, but also behaves according to these norms in any situation, is considered to be morally educated. A morally educated person will have stable moral motives. These motives encourage that person to behave appropriately in society.

Educating the young generation in accordance with the moral qualities that reveal the attitude to society, work, and oneself is a complex process that requires deep knowledge of the educated person, the pedagogical and psychological foundations of moral education. Only the conscious acquisition of moral knowledge will help students to understand what aspects of the behavior of people around them are good and which are bad. Morality is one of the forms of social consciousness and is a set of certain rules of behavior that people living in a certain society must follow.

Morality is manifested in the system of rules of behavior that regulate the behavior of people to each other, to society, to the state, to public property, to the family.

Morality exists as a person's inner world, beliefs, and qualities, while manners are a person's conspicuous manners, behavior, and the level of formation of moral concepts at different ages. Moral values are manifested in moral feelings, especially in hard work. In the rich spiritual heritage of our forefathers, morals have taken a central place in their heritage and creativity. They called morality the "foundation" of society. Therefore, the behavior of each member of the society is paid special attention.

Work requires children to be attentive, sharp minded, resourceful, able to apply learned skills and abilities in practice, and acquire creativity. In the process of work, children have to use a number of concepts and terms that mean certain types of work (actions such as folding a sheet of paper, measuring the required length, cutting a shape according to a template), and describe the consistency of the work done. These enrich the child's speech with new words, allow it to be grammatically correct in a logical manner.

Children should be introduced to the simplest tools and methods of processing materials. Work at MTT prepares them for polytechnic education at school. The moral value of labor is determined by how important it is for society. Work allows every child to understand the social

importance of his work, to enter the life of society, to feel himself a member of this society. Every child should be able to feel that he has his share in the family and children's work. Organization of work in this way educates children in teamwork and discipline, a sense of duty. Therefore, it is important to educate children in teamwork.

Formation of work education in children of preschool age can be achieved by forming the following types of work. may involve:

1. Ethical education through involvement in self-service.
2. Ethical education by teaching household labor.
3. Ethical upbringing by teaching nature to love and respect nature through work in nature.
4. Ethical upbringing by teaching children to work through manual labor and by cultivating feelings of enjoyment and satisfaction from their own work.

Through these methods, the educator forms strong work skills in children. In addition, stories and role-playing games are also important in the process of moral education through labor training. In the fairy tale "Emerald and Precious", the behavior of Precious arouses hatred in the hearts of children. Zumrad's attitude to the environment, hard work, and humility create joy in hearts. Not only Zumrad and Kimmatt fairy tale, but also all Uzbek fairy tales are one of the most important tools to encourage children to work hard, to create goodness, and to form the concepts of manners and ethics in children of preschool age. Labor education of preschool children helps their socialization, forms positive habits, strengthens relationships in the children's community. But it should be remembered that love for work cannot be fully inculcated in a child without the participation of parents. Therefore, joint activities aimed at training labor skills are often held in kindergartens. It harmonizes the child's development, teaches him to respect other people, elders. Labor education of preschool children should be started from a young age. Teachers strive to inculcate in the child a sense of responsibility and duty to complete a certain task, to expand the range of his worldview, morals and interests. In such training, tasks involving self-service, keeping order in the group and in their own closets, as well as observing the rules of personal hygiene are of great importance. Starting from the middle group, children learn to clean dust and take care of plants.

Labor education of preschool children includes not only group games or assignments. Various activities are also held on the grounds, for example, cleaning the kindergarten area (collecting leaves, scraps of paper, sweeping the roads). It should be noted that not only physical strength, but also mental activity is activated during the work process, because the child must understand what sequence of actions must be performed to complete the task. The child begins to think about how to do this task faster and better.

We must not forget that the role of the family is very important in raising children in the spirit of hard work. At home, children should also be given simple tasks and assignments by their parents. The child should be taught to help family members. The child should be entrusted with an easy but responsible task, and then the results of the child's work should be taken seriously.

Labor education of preschool children is one of the most important tasks of any preschool educational organization. Here the child learns about the work of adults and tries to imitate them. At this time, educators must help the child and introduce him to this activity in various ways.

Using a number of methods, adults try to instill in the child a love of work, a desire to help others in some kind of work, respect for results.

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